

Server Side Tagging for Shopify

We have prepared this guide for Shopify merchants to understand what server-side tagging is, whether it is a good fit for them, and what they should do as next steps. Server-Side-Tagging is a data collection and processing method that we will be talking a lot about in the upcoming years. Besides, it will probably be the main way of data-processing.

What is Server-Side Tagging

Server-side tagging has actually been around since the beginning of web analytics and is not a new concept. However, we've been hearing more and more about it after user privacy and cookie restrictions became a major concern, especially with Apple's iOS14 updates.

The majority of data collecting and processing tools, including Google Tag Manager, run on the client-side, that is, in browsers such as Google Chrome. When you visit a website, cookies are loaded, processed, and sent via your browser. Therefore, if a user is running an ad or cookie blocker, tracking will not work properly.

Server-Side Tagging is essential for Shopify stores - especially for the ones that rely on remarketing campaigns.

Client-Side Tracking vs. Server-Side Tracking

Client-Side Tracking is the typical tracking method that almost all websites currently use. Almost every action takes place in the visitor's browser. When a visitor visits our websites, Google Tag Manager (if installed) runs through the browser (e.g. Google Chrome or Safari), reads the data layers (if installed), and sends requests to 3rd parties along with the related data attached to it. If you are not familiar with the classic Google Tag Manager and data layer concept, you can [watch this video](#).

We have prepared a detailed guideline - explained with examples and flow for Shopify Stores

[Learn More](#)

Benefits of Server Side Tagging

Safari & iOS 14 Friendly

Due to Apple's updates, using cookies and tracking in Safari and iOS apps has become more difficult than ever. You can extend the lifetime of cookies by relying on server-side tagging. It will also not be affected by iOS blocking third-party cookies. It affects Shopify merchants that use Facebook and Instagram as marketing channels especially on mobile devices.

Reduces the Impact of Ad Blockers

Many ad blockers block client-side cookies and scripts. Server-side tagging also helps

with that. Ad blockers might be able to block GoogleAnalytics.com and similar requests from your Shopify store but they won't block requests from your own subdomain.

Improves the Page Speed and Reduces the Page Load Time

One of the major negative effects on your page speed comes from third-party JavaScript libraries like Facebook Pixel, Google Analytics, and many others. Instead of installing five different scripts on your site, you will simply upload one script and send it to your server, where it will be processed and shared with third parties. That way, your server-side setup does the heavy lifting and you are not adding too much load on your visitors' browsers.

More Control on the Data

You can control what is being sent while processing data on your server instead of sending it directly to third-party libraries. As an example, the Facebook Pixel tag might collect a lot of information about your users. However, you only need to submit a certain amount of data-set, such as purchase details. You can easily do this filtering on your server-side setup.

Why Use Server Side Tagging for Shopify Stores

Most Shopify stores rely on Facebook and Instagram as their primary marketing channel and source of revenue. Also, remarketing/retargeting campaigns are often the best performing because you're targeting visitors who have already interacted with your Shopify store before, perhaps even purchased a product.

Having the right data is essential for understanding the behavior of your target audience and improving your marketing ROI. For example, if you are running Facebook Ads, you should send your purchase and visitor data to Facebook in the best possible way. This way, you can see your top-performing campaigns and help Facebook optimize your ads based on your data.

Facebook Pixel vs. Facebook Conversion API

- ✔ Facebook Pixel: runs in the user's browser.
- ✔ Facebook Conversion API: works on the server-side and provides more data to your Facebook Pixel.

Facebook Conversion API is created to overcome the tracking challenges - especially the ones that come with iOS 14 updates. It works great with Server-Side Tagging on Shopify.

[Learn More >](#)

How to Setup Server-Side Tagging for Shopify Stores

Server-Side-Tagging setup on Shopify is a complex, technical, and delicate process. It also requires data validation and maintenance. There are several methods to achieve the result. We highly recommend using YOUR OWN Google Cloud Server. This is a very sensitive issue as all your data will pass through the server. Frankly, having your own server will cost between \$60-\$90 or more depending on your traffic, and that may seem like an extra cost. But it's worth it as you'll have full control over your data. We offer a complete server-side tagging setup that includes server-side GTM, Analytics, Google Ads, and FB Conversion API. We help you create your OWN Google Cloud account and then do all of your server-side tagging on your account.

Here is What the Process Looks Like

Step 1: Onboarding & Account Creating

We will assist you (during a video call or by sharing detailed video documentation) with:

- ✔ Creating and connecting your OWN Google Cloud and server-side Google Tag Manager (sGTM) account
- ✔ Linking your own subdomain to Google Cloud account

The Analyzify core version (costs \$179) should already be installed and set up in your store. Because server-side tracking works on top of client-side tracking as described above.

Step 2: Initial Setup & Validation

Data is one of the most sensitive topics for a business. That's why we have a strict data validation phase. Once we've completed the setup, we first submit your data to the test properties while your setup remains intact. Then we cross-compare your original data with the new installation.

- ✔ Analyzify will integrate the related code into your store,
- ✔ All compatible tags will be merged and moved to your new sGTM account,
- ✔ Facebook Conversion API, Google Analytics, Google Ads will be set on the server-side,
- ✔ Your data will flow into the test properties for a few days and be validated.

Step 3: Production & Delivery

Once we are 100% sure that everything is working perfectly, we will disconnect your existing data analytics setup and bring your server-side tagging live.

- ✔ The installation will be pushed to production.
- ✔ The data will be carefully monitored by our experts for the upcoming 4-12 hours.
- ✔ Our team will also walk you through your sGTM installation and provide you with a detailed video series for your specific setup.

One-Time Fee - Including Setup, Validation, Support and, Training

Analyzify Server-Side Tagging is a great deal. We will set up everything for you, validate, deliver, maintain and train your team.

Analyzify Server-Side Tagging Add-on

\$1390

One-time fee per store

[Book a Demo](#)

What does Analyzify Server-Side Tagging Add-on offer?

We do offer a complete server-side tagging setup that includes server-side GTM, Analytics, Google Ads, and FB Conversion API. We ask you to create a Google Cloud account and then do your complete server-side tagging on your account.

How will it work? Where will the data be hosted? Who owns the properties?

Why do I need the core Analyzify (\$179) if I will already have the server-side tagging setup?

What's the total cost and are there any ongoing costs?

What's included:

- Google Cloud Server-Side Tagging Instance Setup
- Google Tag Manager Server-Side Setup
- Google Analytics (UA + GA4),
- Google Ads Server-Side (Enhanced Conversions),
- Facebook Conversion API Setup
- Data Validation / Custom Adjustments
- 12 Months Support
- 2-Hours 1-on-1 Data & Server-Side Tagging Training

- What's the best way to ensure my existing events...
- Why is it better than Shopify's native Facebook Conversion API integration?
- What's the difference between Client-Side tracking and server-side tracking?
- How do you ensure everything will work as expected? How long will it take?
- How do we get started?

What Our Clients Said About Analyzify

We are thrilled to have many happy clients. You can also check the public reviews on Shopify App Store.

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"The analyzify team went beyond just installing G4 through tag manager. When I was trying to do it myself I realized that i needed to spend a lot time on figuring out what events, triggers and tags to install. If i were to do everything that analyzify did i would have had to spend days just learning how and what to do. The video that explains everything that they did and the suggestions given are the icing on the cake. Thank you!"

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"Great app, amazing support, very happy with the purchase. It's great to finally have the proper GTM set up, only regret is that we didn't discover this app sooner. Thanks to the whole team!"

Dog's Lounge

analyzify

We have been working with Shopify clients for a long time in data projects. Our clients' needs inspired us to build the Analyzify Shopify App.

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